

TERRORISM - COMPARISON BETWEEN STRUCTURE OF TERRORISM IN 20TH AND 21ST CENTURY

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ABSTRACT

“Terrorism arises due to political and government instability and youths are attracted by enemy countries”. Terrorism is not a new issue it is oldest form of problem among countries. In the early 20th century the individual terrorist groups are formed in Austria assassinated in 1914. During the First World War Irish volunteers seized parts of central Dublin in the Easter rising. After the first world war it is increased in Middle East. In the 1930s several countries adopted what is termed state terrorism. In 1988 a bomb exploded onboard pan am flight 103, over the Scottish town of Lockerbie. Terror organizations also began looking at targeted Temple visitors. In 1994 Japanese terrorists made use of biological weapons in Matsumoto. In 21st century, in act 2002 Chetthnan rebels took 850 people hostage in a Moscow Theatre. In 2008, Islamic. Terrorists launched a series of attacks in the Indian country. Terrorism is not new and even though it has been used since the early times of recorded history, it can be relatively hard to define terrorist.

Keywords:-Terrorism -Effects- Reasons-20thcentury and 21st century-cold war development

INTRODUCTION

IRA Volunteer the threat of terrorism has steadily increased over the last 30 years. With advances in technology, terrorist acts have become much more destructive and the perpetrators of those act more elusive. Few parts of the world have remained untouched by the current wave of terrorism that began in the late 1960's. This site will explore aspects of both individual level and state terrorism. Individual level terrorism refers to acts of terrorism committed by a person or persons against a society or government to affect political change. State terrorism, or official terrorism, is a label applied to oppressive regimes which systematically commit acts of violence against their own people.

"Terrorism is the unlawful use or threat of violence against persons or property to further political or social objectives. It is usually intended to intimidate or coerce a government, individuals or groups, or to modify their behavior or politics."

--Vice-President's Task Force, 1986

WHAT IS TERRORISM?

Terrorism is not new and even though it has been used since the early times of recorded history, it can be relatively hard to define terrorist.

Terrorism has been described variously as both a tactic and strategy; a crime and a holy duty; a justified reaction to oppression and an inexcusable abomination. Obviously, a lot depends on whose point of view is being represented. Terrorism has often been an effective tactic for the weaker side in a conflict. As an asymmetric form of conflict, it confers coercive power with many of the advantages of military force at a fraction of the cost. Due to the secretive nature and small size of terrorist organizations, they often offer opponents no clear

organization to defend against or to deter.

The history of terrorism is a history of well-known and historically significant individuals, entities, and incidents associated, whether rightly or wrongly, with terrorism. Scholars agree that terrorism is a disputed term, and very few of those labeled terrorists describe themselves as such. It is common for opponents in a violent conflict to describe the other side as terrorists or as practicing terrorism.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

That President Obama won't call it Islamic terrorism; that he believes we shouldn't be on a "high horse" because America and Christians have done bad things; that Muslims are victims of "bigotry and prejudice"; that his State Department says it's the lack of jobs, not religion, that fuels ISIS, should come as no surprise.

"This collective history, this past, directly touches my own," he added. "Not merely because, as a consequence of 9/11, my name is an irresistible target of mocking websites from overzealous Republican operatives. But also because the underlying struggle between worlds of plenty and worlds of want...is the struggle set forth, on a miniature scale, in this book," which at its core is an indictment against Western imperialism, racism and colonialism.

Obama goes on to say he identifies with the "desperation and disorder of the powerless," and how they can "easily slip into violence and despair."

- 1) The regions with long term terrorist activities have been *Jammu and Kashmir*, *east-central* and south-central India (Naxalism) and the Seven Sister States. In August 2008, National Security Advisor M K Narayanan has said that there are as many as 800 terrorist cells operating in the country. As of 2013, 205 of the country's 608 districts were affected by terrorist activity. Terror attacks caused 231 civilian deaths in 2012 in India, compared to 11,098 terror-caused deaths worldwide, according to the State Department of the United States; or about 2% of global terror fatalities while it accounts for 17.5% of global population.

Terrorism is an anxiety-inspiring method of repeated violent action, employed by (semi-) clandestine individual, group or state actors, for idiosyncratic, criminal or political reasons, whereby the direct targets of violence are not the main targets. The immediate human victims of violence are generally chosen randomly (targets of opportunity) or selectively (representative or symbolic targets) from a target population, and serve as message generators. Threat and violence-based communication processes between terrorist organization, victims, and main targets are used to manipulate the main target (audience(s)), turning it into a target of terror, a target of demands, or a target of attention, depending on whether intimidation, coercion, or propaganda is primarily sought

Statement of the problem

REASONS FOR TERRORISM

There are many reasons why people have chosen to resort to terrorist tactics over the years. In general terms the terrorist group will make use of these tactics, rather than non-violent methods, as they may: Feel that there is no alternative but to use force. Feel that these tactics have the potential to force change. View the use of terror as appropriate 'revenge' against a perceived enemy. The effects of terrorism include the injuries, deaths and psychological trauma of the immediate victims; short- and long-term impact on the economy of the attacked country; and enhanced security, military and intelligence activities to deter future attacks. Terrorism also often creates publicity for the groups or individuals initiating the attacks,

which is often their objective.

Besides the injuries and deaths immediately brought about by terrorist attacks, survivors often suffer from post-traumatic stress disorder, anxiety and major depression. The economy suffers an immediate impact due to building and infrastructure damage, but it also suffers long-term effects from trauma to financial markets, a rise in spending on security and defense, and the impact on supply chains of enhanced security at land, sea and air border crossings. Equipping the military and police for retaliation and defense includes the passing of legislation that targets terrorists, deportation of unregistered aliens, granting of additional powers to police and military, fewer restrictions on the detention and interrogation of suspects, and possible direct military or police action to eliminate perceived threats. It also may include the creation of new agencies or enhancement of existing agencies to screen mail and other forms of communication and to guard essential national and local infrastructures.

Pre-Modern Terrorist Groups

Terrorism is best understood as a modern phenomenon: as violent struggle between non-state organizations and modern states, and because it relies on mass media to spread terror among as many people as possible. However, there are some pre-modern groups who used terror to achieve political ends, and who are often considered pre-cursors to modern terrorists:

Religious-Political

There has been a rise in religiosity globally since the 1970s and with it, a rise in what many analysts call religious terrorism . It would be more accurate to call groups such as Al Qaeda religious-political, or religious-nationalist. We call them religious because they use a religious idiom and shape their 'mandate' in divine terms. Their goals however, are political: recognition, power, territory, concessions from states, and the like. Historically, such groups have included:

EFFECTS OF TERRORISM

1. Social and political injustice: People choose terrorism when they are trying to right what they perceive to be a social or political or historical wrong—when they have been stripped of their land or rights, or denied these.
2. The belief that violence or its threat will be effective, and usher in change. Another way of saying this is: the belief that violent means justify the ends. Many terrorists in history said sincerely that they chose violence after long deliberation, because they felt they had no choice. What are the causes of terrorism?

Examples:

- a) The IRA used force partly because the democratic process, in their view, had failed and was unlikely to result in any positive outcome. The actions of the British Government and Armed Forces, in their opinion, proved this and as the Government response to calls for improvements etc hardened, so to did their 'need' to use terror tactics.
- b) Zionist groups bombed British targets in Palestine in the 1930's as they felt this would prompt the British and the International community into creating an independent Jewish State.
- c) The Popular Front for the Liberation of Palestine used violence against the Israeli's as they felt this was legitimate given that the Israeli's occupied what they considered to be their land.

Social Reasons:

In areas where there are minority groups there have been incidences of terrorism emerging as a result of these groups not being granted adequate rights or as a result of seeing their culture destroyed. One example of this being the case is the Tamil Tigers in Sri Lanka who fought to have an independent nation for the Tamils.

Objective of the study

- 1) morale-building within the terrorist group
- 2) The second objective is advertising
- 3) *Disorientation*
- 4) Provoking a response by the incumbent group
- 5) Cold War Developments

Terrorism in the 20th and 21st Century

The Early 20th Century

The first half of the 20th century saw two events that influenced the nature of conflict to the present day. The effects of two World Wars inflamed passions and hopes of nationalists throughout the world, and severely damaged the legitimacy of the international order and governments. Nationalism on the Rise Nationalism intensified during the early 20th century throughout the world. It became an especially powerful force in the subject peoples of various colonial empires. Although dissent and resistance were common in many colonial possessions, and sometimes resulted in open warfare, nationalist identities became a focal point for these actions.

Cold War Developments

The bi-polar world of the Cold War changed perception of conflicts the world over. Relatively minor confrontations took on significance as arenas where the superpowers could compete without risking escalation to full nuclear war. Warfare between the East and the West took place on the peripheries, and was limited in scope to prevent escalation. During the immediate postwar period, terrorism was more of a tactical choice by leaders of nationalist insurgencies and revolutions. Successful campaigns for independence from colonial rule occurred throughout the world, and many employed terrorism as a supporting tactic. When terrorism was used, it was used within the framework of larger movements, and coordinated with political, social, and military action. Even when terrorism came to dominate the other aspects of a nationalist struggle, such as the Palestinian campaign against Israel, it was (and is) combined with other activities. The Internationalization of Terror. The age of modern terrorism might be said to have begun in 1968 when the Popular Front for the Liberation of Palestine (PFLP) hijacked an El Al airliner en route from Tel Aviv to Rome. While hijackings of airliners had occurred before, this was the first time that the nationality of the carrier (Israeli) and its symbolic value was a specific operational aim. Also a first was the deliberate use of the passengers as hostages for demands made publicly against the Israeli government. The combination of these unique events, added to the international scope of the operation, gained significant media attention. The founder of PFLP, Dr. George Habash observed that the level of coverage was tremendously greater than battles with Israeli soldiers in their previous area of operations. "At least the world is talking about us now."

Current State of Terrorism

The largest act of international terrorism occurred on September 11, 2001 in a set of coordinate attacks on the United States of America, where Islamic terrorists hijacked civilian airliners and used them to attack the World Trade Centre (WTC) towers in New York City and the Pentagon in Washington, DC. The effects of 9/11 had a significant impact on the American psyche and led to global reverberations. Other major terrorist attacks have also occurred in New Delhi (Indian Parliament attacked); Bali car bomb attack; London subway bombings; Madrid train station bombings; attacks in Mumbai (hotels, train station and a Jewish outreach centre), Nigeria, Pakistan, Paris, and more. The operational and strategic epicenter of Islamic terrorism is mostly centered in Pakistan, Afghanistan and parts of Syria. Refer to our blog for more recent terror incidents and analysis.

CONCLUSION

Terrorism is an international problem in today's global community. Many nations are affected, whether directly or indirectly. Most nations oppose terrorism, while others condone or even support active, brutal terrorism and terrorist groups. Terrorism is defined by the US State Department to contain four elements. The first is a threat of violence or an act of violence. Next is a political objective. Third is that violence and threat of violence is a direct attack on civilians making civilians a primary target. Lastly, it is perpetrated by a supporting a nation or nations of terrorism. Two examples of terrorism and non terrorism are: the bombing of the US Embassy in Dar-Es-Salaam and the dropping of the atomic bomb on Hiroshima and Nagasaki. In the Dar-Es-Salaam bombing, it is believed that there is one sub national actor involved: Osama bin Laden. With Nagasaki and Hiroshima, the US State Department agreed to drop the bomb. This was a general agreement of the American government, a national actor. Though both fit three criteria for a terrorist attack, the US government's general decision to drop the bomb automatically makes it an act of war, not terrorism. One of the goals of terrorism is to make the terrorist's views heard. This can be caused by a total media blitz that usually occurs after a terrorist attack. The media is an excellent window for the terrorists to shout their demands and views immediately after an attack.

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